

Office of the Controller General of Patents, Designs & Trade Marks
Department of Industrial Policy & Promotion,
Ministry of Commerce & Industry,
Government of India

Application Details

APPLICATION NUMBER	202321017750
APPLICATION TYPE	ORDINARY APPLICATION
DATE OF FILING	16/03/2023
APPLICANT NAME	1 . Swapnali Kulkarni 2 . Dr. Krishna Kumar TP 3 . Dr. Vinayak Anil Bhat 4 . Dr. Pallavi Ghanshyala Vyas 5 . Dr. D. Sanjeeva Rao 6 . Dr. T. Snehalatha 7 . Dr. E. Karthika 8 . Dr. P. Rajasekar
TITLE OF INVENTION	TRANSGENDER PEOPLE AND HEALTHCARE BARRIERS
FIELD OF INVENTION	GENDER EQUALITY
E-MAIL (As Per Record)	swapnalikulkarni31@gmail.com
ADDITIONAL-EMAIL (As Per Record)	swapnalikulkarni31@gmail.com
E-MAIL (UPDATED Online)	
PRIORITY DATE	
REQUEST FOR EXAMINATION DATE	--
PUBLICATION DATE (U/S 11A)	31/03/2023